

An Assessment of Design and Construction Methodology of Deep Excavation with Inclined Struts.

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Abstract— this study analyzed the deep excavation to improve and standardize a finite element method (FEM) for the deep foundation in Muscat, Oman. Also, to compare the earth pressure distribution and extant transferred to the contiguous bored pile based on simplified method. The main scope of this project is to understand and design an efficient support system to ensure that the lateral displacement of the surrounding soil is rigid and limited. Also, to apply the standards of the Oman deep foundation building code in the building analysis. This study focused on the designing methodologies for the contiguous pile supported with struts to stabilize the deep excavation, while it's used to hold the excavations of 8.05m, 10.05m, 11.5m and 12.55m depth. To conclude that, Plaxis provides more accurate displacement data for the deep foundation such as: diaphragm wall, pile wall, retaining wall, etc. This analysis of Plaxis can benefit the engineers to provide more time because it is more simply than other method, can be more economically because it is minimizing the structure design and can provide more design options. (*Abstract*)

Keywords—*Deep excavation, Inclined Struts, Displacement, FEM, ETABS, PLAXIS 2D, Soil Stability.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Analysis the deep excavation to improve and standardize a finite element method (FEM) for the deep foundation in Muscat, Oman. Also, to compare the earth pressure distribution and extant transferred to the contiguous bored pile based on simplified method The demand of engineering projects is increasing day by day in the world which requires application of new designing technologies. The increasing of the population, transportation-system and environment issues needs to develop the underground structures in the crowded area due to the demand of infrastructure expansion. However, the deep excavations number in the urban area is growth yearly. It is considered as a formidable scheme because of several factors such as structure surround the project (streets or buildings) and the project designed with vary deep underground stories. In Chile, since 1990, in Santiago the underground depth was from 10-13 m. Nowadays, it has been changed in the depth of the underground level. For example, Costanera center building has 20m depth which contain 5 underground stories. Furthermore, other building with the depth of 25m included 7 underground stories, the name of the building is Titanium tawer. On another hand, the depth has been increased to 32m in Territoria building with 9 underground stories [1]. As a study done by Saitama University, 2019, Japan, on the diaphragm wall for factory building consist of four

underground floors (basement) in Qatar. The depth of planned excavation is 16 m. the diaphragm wall was analyzed by software program (PLAXIS 2D), this study shows the deflection limit of wall acceptable which is supported by the ground anchors. At first, all sides of the retaining wall were considered to be supported by anchors but because of the nearby of existing buildings 1 section replaced to inclined struts, the steel inclined struts was established in 1 side because of the impossibility of anchor construct due to inaccessible area in the neighbor structure. The inclined struts were considered as a fix end anchor when modeling through PLAXIS 2d while the space between each strut is 7.5m. According to Clough & Rourke from the historical cases the wall displacement must be less than 2% of the excavation depth. The geotechnical reports of the site was offered by the owner, the ground soil consists of silty to gravely sand also included Cap-rock, Midra Shale, Rus Formation and Limestone. Also, the stratum factor was based on historical soil geotechnics reports of surrounded soil structures. This study focused on the method of wall design, in addition, the important of providing the surrounded area (existing building) details. At 2 sides there is a variance between the wall deflection measured and analyzed wall because of installation the pile closes to shoring wall. At the three section the Max horizontal deflection of the retaining wall is 0.25%. the other section recording 0.05% and 0.08% wall deflection [3].

The following journals done by Z.Sabzi & A. Fakher, 2017 studied the struts performance in supporting the structure lateral load and minimize the deflection. In addition, the struts spacing and struts effective installation was proposed. The guideline displacement design is provided built on the result information of numerical study which detailed from the site measurement (field data). furthermore, 3 investigated point was established to provide the soil information. The site soil is consisting of two layer, stiff-clay silt and stiff-silty clay without water table along the excavation area. The stiff-clay silt which is 8 m depth affected the behaviors of excavation. It is mentioned that the effect of struts support by decreasing the deformation amount is almost same as diaphragm wall effect. Thus, the study showed strongly decreasing of the horizontally deflection close to ground level. At the point of the installation, which was in the max wall deflection, without the struts support system the surrounded excavation vertical cut area will resist a large horizontal load. the struts-arch was clearly shown in struts corner which led to minimize the lateral stress loads at vicinity struts installed points. The plastic-strains progress showed that a plastic area started to

take shape close to underside of the front of excavation at excavation middle length. Moreover, the rises of struts-intervals numbers cause an increasing the lateral deflection along the excavation wall. However, the larger space between struts must not be more than the depth of the excavation. Also, the load-bearing-ratio found through divided the struts unite load by adjacent structure unite load. Which revealed that, when the struts spaces increase the ratio of the load bearing decrease because of the strut's square intervals. Along the excavation face, the most effective struts installation points to provide the maximum decreasing in the lateral load are the middle struts, so, it should be at the first installation stages if unavailability to install all struts at one time [4]. A paper done by P.Long, 2011 describes the difficulty of the traditional methods to analysis and design some of underground soil stability cases. This study compared and discussed the results of finite element method for sheet-pile walls and the traditional methods. The new program as Plaxis 2d simplify the design the optimum formation of the multi propped sheet pile wall. The difficulty is to design the pre-stresses loads which aimed to minimize the bending moment, lateral soil movement as well the shear stress. Also, the traditional methods design for overestimated in several cases while the bending moment is underestimated in certain cases. The results of this study showed that for the finite element methods can provide a full design and analysis for the sheet pile wall, soil and the interaction between the soil and the wall. Also, at each construction stages, the model gives an ability to analysis the soil and wall interaction. Finite element methods model can be a verify the Rankine methods for passive and active sides when in this study it is clearly showed the active and passive side of the anchore vicinity passively at variance the concept of Rankine which presented as active soil side. Furthermore, the choosing of the prestress anchored load from the first excavation stage not importantly as the final excavation stage which shows the anchore load at the maximum stress. at the last stage of excavation, it is important to choose the correct prestress load for the anchore which clearly can decrease the lateral load, soil movement, bending moment and shear force along the sheet pile wall. For the sheet pile (steel) it showed overestimated analysis design for the traditional methods bending moment. In some cases, design an inclined steel struts could be additional realistically, as a structure surrounded by existing buildings. In Oman, the Airport control tower structure is the highest building with the deepest foundation while most of the residential building structures consists of 2-4 stories because of the large area of the country which is 309501 km² comparing with its population 5.199,610 million in 2021 [15]. This results a significant increasing in the areas of structures, but the heights of the buildings are limited, which decrease the deep of foundations. On other hand, projects such as Metro, Airports, Tall Buildings, and Ports must include a deep excavation works [3].

It is useful to use the underground levels to provide more spaces in the building area, which needs to interim retaining framework because of the vertical excavation cuts in the site area. The aim of this study is to understand and design an efficient support system to ensure that the lateral displacement of the surrounding soil is rigid and limited. In Oman, the Concrete pile wall with struts is most widely used for the soil-dense in the absence of the ground water table.

Insite retaining pile installation is common because of it is practicability and availability.

There are several forms of the in site retaining piles. For instance, the contiguous (intermittent)

pile wall used for cohesive soil with absence of water table. as shown in figure 1, The spaces between the piles are more than the diameters of the piles. Popular diameter of the piles is 0.60m, 0.80m and 1.00m. furthermore, the waler beam is used in most of cases supported by anchors or struts, it is commonly consisting of concrete but in some cases the use of steel is possible. The significant uses of diagonal Struts in Oman are more than the anchored piled wall due to the difficult approval from neighbor's area, especially in sites surrounded by buildings [4].

To ensure a constancy deep excavation the soil stress-state and pile deformation must be provide. Also, through the Numerical-Models the soil stress-state can be presents or by studying historical cases using simplified model depended to equilibrium limit (approximate method). But there is miss enough historical data to ensure the approximate method for the dense soil for more than 7m. the numerical models can directly deform the performance of the pile [1].

The technology development of the construction as well the computer programs simplified the design process of the shallow excavations (more than 6m depth) which deems as deep excavations. However, the deformation and position of the excavation is not important anymore. The type of the retaining wall system selected depend upon the soil condition, the mobility to the site for machinery, the surrounded structures and the depth of excavation [5].

contiguous pile wall is suitable options for shallow excavation surrounded by existing building. Historically, it was start used in 1900s, currently its significantly increases because of it is efficiency for deep foundation. For the safety of the excavation and the adjacent structures the wall movement (displacement) is the most important factors. However, the common range value of the wall horizontal displacement should be less than 2% of the underground structure excavation depth. Even so, in case of the supports nears to neighbor structure/building, the lateral wall movement of 2% is not appropriate. The different of sites deformation such as soil condition, neighboring buildings, substructure data of adjacent buildings and the depth of excavation from site to site provide an availability for the designers to study and increase the designing for the upcoming projects. This paper presents a case-study of deep excavation located in Muscat, Oman which is supported by a contiguous pile wall with incline struts connected by walling beam where it is applied to resist the lateral wall movement.

II. MODELS USED

PLAXIS 2d & 3d consider as a most important computer program for the geotechnical analysis. Also, it is significantly used for the cases of the soil mechanics such as support of deep excavation.

It is analyzing the stabilities and deformations in geotechnics engineering and the mechanics of rocks by two- or three-dimensional analysis. Furthermore, the program is world famous and used by the universities and college in geotechnics field and best of engineering firms because of

the data information availability. However, it is covering embankments, foundation, tunnelling, excavation, and reservoir-geomechanics. Overall, PLAXIS allows the users to create a model with high-speed and more efficiency [2]. Moreover, ETABS program used find the wall displacement, the displacement by using active passive force analysis. The result of total horizontal displacement according to ETABS models is established to analyzed most of the structure elements based on the input data and codes used. Moreover, Etabs present an output result for multistory, beams and columns 2D & 3D analysis including the final total displacement of the structure.

III. COMPUTATION THE LATERAL LOAD

For computing the forces for the contiguous pile wall must analysis the forces as a cantilever and equilibrium. This method is used by Rankine to assume the passive and active sides. After that, by using Etabs Software the maximum approximated lateral displacement is simply provided. The infrastructure soil of the site has a density of (γ) = 17 KN/m³, with fraction angle of (ϕ) = 30.

IV. WALL\SIDE A

A. Wall A lateral load by traditional method

a) For computing the forces for the contiguous pile wall must analysis the forces as a cantilever and equilibrium. This method is used by Rankine to assume the passive and active sides. After that, by using Etabs Software the maximum approximated lateral displacement is simply provided. The infrastructure soil of the site has a density of (γ) = 17 KN/m³, with fraction angle of (ϕ) = 30

According to theory of Rankine passive and active soil:

$$K_a = 1 - \sin \phi, \quad K_p = 1 / K_a \quad (1)$$

The forces of the active and passive side are determined at the following formulas:

$$P_i = Y x K_a x H_i \quad (2)$$

$$P_{a2i} = Y x K_a x (H_i + D_i) \quad (3)$$

Fig. 1. Passive and active pressure & the point of rotation

$$A1 = 1/2 H P A \quad (4)$$

$$A2 = (P a + P a2) D / 2 \quad (5)$$

$$A3 = (P e + P j) S / 2 \quad (6)$$

After calculation of areas, by obtain the subtraction area the relationship of D & S provided as function. Also, by finding the moment relationship the second relationship by D & S provided, these two function allowed to find the valued of D. in addition, by calculated (X) Max moment located at zero pressure using these formulas

$$0 = \frac{P a1}{y (Y K_p - Y K_a)} \quad (7)$$

$$[(P a1 x H) / 2 + (P a1 x y) / 2 = X (Y K_p - Y K_a) X / 2] \quad (8)$$

$$M_{max} = [(H p a / 2) (H / 3 + y + x)] + [(p a y / 2) (2 / 3 y + x)] - [(Pressure at X) (X / 3)], \quad (9)$$

$$Pressure \text{ at } x = [Y X (K_p - K_a) x / 2] \quad (10)$$

For minimum section modulus,

$$S = \frac{M_{max}}{\sigma_{all}} \quad (11)$$

After computing the forces using ETABS to find the wall displacement, the displacement by using active passive force analysis. Figure 3 shows the result of total horizontal displacement according to ETABS models. ETABS is established to analyzed most of the structure elements based on the input data and codes used. Also, ETABS Present an output result for multistory, beams and columns 2D & 3D analysis including the final total displacement of the structure, walls, retaining walls and concrete or steel frame.

Fig. 2. The maximum displacement for wall A

Another simple method to determine the wall displacement by using Plaxis2d model, Plaxis is software model program present FEM finite-element models analyzes based on geotechnic study, deformations, stability of soil and displacement of soil structure. At the final procedure, plaxis provide full presentations of model results. In this study after applying the soil data and plate (Pile) details through plaxis program under Mohr-coulomb material set, the following figures shows the total displacement for the 4 walls. The struts are presented as a fix-end anchor. According to PLAXIS output model, the final horizontal displacement for wall A showed in Figure 3.

Fig. 3. Wall A soil and plate deformation

B. Wall displacement without supporting system

Wall A ANALYSIS

As the traditional method and Plaxis2d design, Wall B, Wall C and wall D exceed the limit of displacement with less than (2% of excavated length).

For wall A

$$2/100 \times 8.08 \text{ m} = 0.161 \text{ m} = 161.0 \text{ mm}$$

Total displacement according to traditional method = 31.62 mm

Total displacement according to PLAXIS2d = 16.16 mm
 $16.16 \text{ mm} < 31.62 \text{ mm} < 161 \text{ mm}$

So, Wall A not required supporting system because of low designed displacement length.

Table. 1. Total displacement according for 2 methods

ANALYSIS METHOD USED	TOTAL DISPLACEMENT ACCORDING TO TOW METHODS (mm)			maximum displacement limit (2% of excavated length)
	ETABS	PLAXIS 2D		
WALL A	31.62	16.16		161
WALL B	24.98	16.39		201
WALL C	54.22	16		230
WALL D	417.25	82.55		251

CONCLUSION

This study focused on the designing methodologies for the contiguous pile supported with struts to stabilize the deep excavation, while it's used to hold the excavations of 8.05m, 10.05m, 11.5m and 12.55m depth. In addition, the study showed the important of investigate the characteristics of structure substructure and superstructure, which significantly affect the design of the supporting system. Moreover, the previous study draws a standard for the geotechnical engineers to design of struts (inclined struts) support system by different methods.

The case study separated to four main deep walls according to its depths and the adjacent exiting structure. Plaxis 2d software analyzed all walls depending on the surcharge load, wall dimension and struts adjusting. Etabs software used to analyze the wall after uploading the load from the traditional method to determine the total lateral displacement. The calculated load applied to struts determined by the method of Rinkine.

For wall A, the Plaxis model showed less horizontal displacement than the traditional method. according to the literature, Plaxis models are more accurate to the real measurement while wall B as the design showed significantly different on the lateral displacement, when the design of the Plaxis provide less deflection in the pile wall. Wall C also showed on the plaxis design provide less horizontal displacement. Wall D the only wall surrounded by existing building with surcharge load of 250 KN/m, the design of it showed significant different while on the traditional method the wall displacement is not acceptable when the Plaxis model showed an acceptable limit which is under the 2% of the excavation depth.

To conclude that, Plaxis provides more accurate displacement data for the deep foundation such as: diaphragm wall, pile wall, retaining wall, etc. This analysis of Plaxis can benefits the engineers to provide more time because it is more simply than other method, can be more economically because it is minimizing the structure design and it can provide more design options.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The work presented here was carried out under the supervision of Prof. Dr. Tuncer Çelik, and Co-Advisor Dr. Seyed Mohsen Seyedi Viand, Department of Civil Engineering, ALTINBAS University in TURKEY. The author would like to express his deep gratitude to the advisors for their patient advice and loving encouragement from the beginning to the end of the master and not just in the thesis.

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